

pyteea - A Python-based Toolbox for Automated Technical, Economic and Environmental Assessment

pyteea is an overarching Python toolbox that integrates all underlying libraries of the toolbox chain to enable comprehensive techno-economic analysis (TEA) and life-cycle assessment (LCA) of chemical processes. It supports both single-point evaluations and the systematic assessment of entire parameter studies, providing a unified framework for technical, economic, and environmental analysis.

The toolbox incorporates heat integration capabilities to ensure the technical feasibility of modeled processes and to consistently account for energy integration effects within economic and life-cycle calculations. By combining simulation data, cost models, environmental metrics, and process integration methods, pyteea offers a coherent and extensible platform for advanced process assessment.

To improve accessibility and usability, pyteea provides a graphical user interface (GUI) that guides users through the setup, execution, and evaluation of analyses. The GUI abstracts the complexity of the underlying toolchain while still allowing advanced users to access and customize all configuration options.

Key Features

- Integrated TEA and LCA framework
 - Combined economic and environmental assessment of chemical processes
 - Support for single evaluations and full parameter study analyses
- Toolchain integration
 - Unified use of all underlying libraries for simulation access, costing, unit handling, and data management
 - Consistent data flow across technical, economic, and ecological modules
- Heat integration
 - Evaluation and integration of heat recovery and energy coupling options
 - Ensures technical feasibility and consistency in TEA and LCA calculations
- Graphical user interface (GUI)
 - User-friendly access to technical, economic, and ecological analyses
 - Simplified setup of simulations, parameter studies, and evaluations
- Parameter study management
 - Execution of automated parameter studies directly from the GUI
 - Assisted generation of required configuration files
- Configuration and evaluation support
 - Guided creation of configuration files for TEA, LCA, and heat integration
 - Structured evaluation and visualization of parameter study results

Requirements

The tool requires the two in-house repositories [pyteeatea](#), [pyteealca](#), and [pyteeasc](#). Their required version together with additionally required publicly available libraries are listed below.

```
dependencies = [  
    "pyteeatea @ git+https://...pyteeatea.git@0.2.4",  
    "pyteealca @ git+https://.../pyteealca.git@0.2.3",  
    "pyteeasc @ git+https://.../pyteeasc.git@0.2.5",  
    "numpy>=1.24.3",  
    "loguru>=0.6.0",  
    "pandas>=2.0.1",  
    "psutil>=5.9.5",  
    "pydantic>=2.6.2",  
    "pywin32>=304",  
    "pytest>=7.3.1",  
    "pytz>=2022.6",  
    "PyYAML>=6.0",  
    "ruamel.yaml>=0.18.15",  
    "streamlit>=1.51.0",  
    "streamlit-ace>=0.1.1",  
    "streamlit-aggrid>=1.2.1",  
    "pyside6>=6.7.0",  
    "kaleido>=0.2.1",  
    "plotly>=5.19.0",  
    "seaborn>=0.13.2"  
]  
requires-python = ">=3.10"
```

Usages

Load/Save previous settings

For increased usability the previous configurations can be stored and loaded via the Home page of the tool.

pyteea

Python-based Techno-economic and Environmental Assessment

Go directly to the various assessment tools or start with defining your run settings for a new parameter run

> Load previously saved cache files

> Save current cache files

Execution of Parameter Runs

A detailed description can be found in [pyteeasc](#).

Evaluation of parameter study

The main configuration file for initializing the evaluation object looks like follows:

```
config_type: EvaluationObject
config_version: 0.0.2
name: example_eval
logger:
  log_file: ..\log_files\pyteea_report.log
  log_level: 1
  colorize: false
eval_settings:
  overwrite_result_dirs: false
var_info:
  var_run_path: path\to\variation_run_results
  name: prev_def
  single_run: false
  load_full_data: false
tea:
  active: true
  tea_file_locations: tea_files\config_files\tea_file_locations.yml
  additional_record_items: []
  additional_eval:
    npc: true
lca:
  active: true
  lca_file_locations: lca_files\config_files\lca_file_locations.yml
tech:
  active: true
  flow_diagrams:
```

```
    config_file: flowdiagram_files\sankey_cfg.yml
hi:
  active: true
  hi_file_locations: hi_files\hi_config_file.yml
```

Eval single parameter run

To eval a specific parameter run, the EvalObject has to be initialized by providing the path to its main configuration file. Subsequently, the object's functions can be triggered to run single runs via the run's run number or uuid.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pytea import eval_obj as eo
```

```
eval_obj = eo.get_eval_obj(eval_config=Path('path/to/eval_cfg.yml'))
eval_obj.eval_single_run(0)
eval_obj.export_run_results()
```

Eval full parameter run

To eval a specific parameter run, the EvalObject has to be initialized by providing the path to its main configuration file. Subsequently, the object's functions can be triggered to run single runs via the run's run number or uuid.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pytea import eval_obj as eo
```

```
eval_obj = eo.get_eval_obj(eval_config=Path('path/to/eval_cfg.yml'))
eval_obj.eval_var_run()
eval_obj.export_run_results()
```

Technical Evaluation

The library offers the tabular visualisation of stream and block data to analyze specific or a group stream in detail. Additionally, after a GUI-assisted definition, automated composition plots and sankey diagrams can be created.

Figure: Technical Evaluation

Heat integration

To ensure a technical feasibility of the processes for all parameter combinations, a heat integration is crucial. Hence, this option has been implemented into the toolbox in order to assess the available heat and to integrate potentially required heating or cooling utilities. Furthermore, they can be integrated into the economic or environmental calculations.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pytea import eval_obj as eo
```

```
eval_obj = eo.get_eval_obj(eval_config=Path('path/to/eval_cfg.yml'))
eval_obj.eval_hi(0)
eval_obj.export_run_results()
```


Figure: Heat Integration

Economic Analysis

After setting up the economic configuration files according to pyteeatea, a single run or the whole variation run can be assessed economically. The tool comes with a list of predefined postprocessing features such as: - Data Cleaning - Data Extraction (from the individual variation runs) - Costs Data Visualization - Correlation Matrix

Furthermore, it always the user to extract specific data in CSV format for individual postprocessing.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteea import eval_obj as eo
```

```
eval_obj = eo.get_eval_obj(eval_config=Path('path/to/eval_cfg.yml'))
eval_obj.eval_tea(0)
eval_obj.export_run_results()
```

- Home
- Edit Run Settings
- Run Execution
- Evaluation Settings
- Heat integration
- Technical results
- Economic analysis - Single**
- Economic analysis - Var. Run
- Environmental results
- Additional pages

Select run_id:

91ec7c234e26254cb3...

Single run analysis

- Charts**
- Equipments
- Raw Materials & Utilities
- Byproducts
- Net Production Costs
- Post processing

Economic evaluation

Variation run: 'b1a135b8324f955e8774235e0676f913'

Rerun economic calculation

Debug Mode

syngas_train	biomass input	electrolyser	meoh-mode	meoh-mode-2	meoh_icl_reactor_design
91ec7c234e26254cb341b85ebe747c9b	1	0	2	40-15-IC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Integrate HI in TEA

Equipments Rmu Byproducts Npc

Equipments

Fixed Capital Investment 209204782.35 EUR

Figure: Economic Evaluation

Environmental Assessment

After setting up the environmental configuration files according to pyteealca, a single run or the whole variation run can be assessed environmentally.

```
from pathlib import Path
from pyteea import eval_obj as eo
```

```
eval_obj = eo.get_eval_obj(eval_config=Path('path/to/eval_cfg.yml'))
eval_obj.eval_lca(0)
eval_obj.export_run_results()
```

Graphical visualization of LCA results

- Home
- Edit Run Settings
- Run Execution
- Evaluation Settings
- Heat integration
- Technical results
- Economic analysis - Single
- Economic analysis - Var. Run
- Environmental results**
- Additional pages

Select run_id:

91ec7c234e26254cb3...

Environmental evaluation

Variation run: 'b1a135b8324f955e8774235e0676f913'

syngas_train	biomass input	electrolyser	meoh-mode	meoh-mode-2	meoh_icl_reactor_design
91ec7c234e26254cb341b85ebe747c9b	1	0	2	40-15-IC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Data has been read from a previous LCA. Do you want to rerun it?

Select grouping method for LCA plots

ProcessStep

Select a LCIA you want to investigate:

('EF v3.1', 'climate change', 'global warming potential (GWP100)', 'kg CO2-Eq')

('EF v3.1', 'climate change', 'global warming potential (GWP100)')

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